

Sponge City Development in Accra: A Sustainable Solution in Mitigating Perennial Flooding

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Abstract

Accra, the capital city of Ghana, has been plagued by perennial flooding due to rapid urbanization, poor drainage systems, Lack of planning, and low law enforcement. The Sponge City Concept (SPC), initiated in China, has shown good promise as a sustainable solution to these challenges by integrating natural water management systems into urban design. This paper explores the potential of Sponge City development in Accra as a solution to the lost rightful approach to addressing the flood situation in Accra, drawing lessons from China's experiences and global best practices. The study employs primary and secondary data sources. Primary data were collected through interviews, focus group discussions, and consultations with key stakeholders in the field. Secondary materials were obtained from government reports, and reputable academic databases, including but not limited to Elsevier, Springer Nature, ResearchGate, and Google Scholar. The historical context of flooding in Accra, the conceptual framework of Sponge Cities, and the challenges and opportunities for implementation are discussed to provide insight. By adopting Sponge City principles, Authorities stand a very high chance of mitigating flooding, enhancing water resource management, and promoting sustainable urban development, as it is in sync with the UN SDGs as part of global efforts to reach sustainable Urbanization, Environment protection, and improved climate resilience. Learning from China's experiences and global best practices, Accra can develop a localized Sponge City model to suit Accra's peculiar case and address its hydrological and urban development challenges.

Keywords: *Sponge City, Flooding, Wetland, Water Management, Urbanization.*

Suggested citation: De-Souza, R., Msuya, A.S., Bojang, O.A., & Olamilekan, O.S. (2025). Sponge City Development in Accra: A Sustainable Solution in Mitigating Perennial Flooding. *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 2(2), 122-132. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2025.2(2).12

Introduction

In recent decades, flooding has emerged as a global crisis that significantly impedes economic and social development. This widespread phenomenon has resulted in substantial loss of life and economic damage across various countries (Asumadu-Sarkodie et al., 2017). One notable example is Ghana, where floods have been constantly recurring, particularly within the capital city of Accra. Accra's rapid urbanization has destroyed natural wetlands and water-holding mechanisms, worsening the city's vulnerability to flooding and resulting in loss of life and property (Amaglo et al., 2022). The National Disaster Management Organization (NADMO) reported over 150 deaths and significant property damage worth Millions of Ghana Cedis, in the 2015 June 3rd flooding incident (Asamoah, 2023). This highlights the urgent need for innovative solutions to urban water management (He et al., 2021; Larsen et al., 2016).

Certain scholars have attributed the recurring floods to the Ghanaian government's implementation of the Structural Adjustment Program (SAP) (Afeku, 2005). Others have cited the intensity of rainfall events across eight drainage basins in Accra (Asumadu-Sarkodie et al., 2017). Some have criticized ineffective and uncoordinated land use planning, obstructed waterways, and poorly designed, makeshift engineering projects due to various institutional constraints and irregular weather patterns (Amaglo et al., 2022; Gaisie & Cobbinah, 2023; Owusu & Obour, 2021). The phenomenon of flooding in Accra presents a multifaceted challenge that necessitates a comprehensive examination of various contributing factors. To effectively address this issue, pragmatic and robust engineering solutions are urgently needed. A holistic and integrated approach to flood management is essential, one that encompasses the unique characteristics of the local physical, social, and political contexts (Amoako & Frimpong Boamah, 2015). This paper examines the potential of Sponge City development in Accra, drawing on China's experiences and global examples to propose a feasible solution to the city's flooding crisis.

The Sponge City concept, which originated in China, provides a sustainable approach to managing urban rainwater through natural accumulation, infiltration, and purification (Jiang et al., 2018; Li et al., 2017). This concept aligns well with several SDGs since it focuses on sustainable urban development, climate resilience, and environmental protection. Key SDGs that align with the sponge city concepts are: SDG 6, which addresses clean water and sanitation, SDG 11, addressing sustainable cities and communities, SDG 13, addressing climate change, and SDG 15, addressing life on land.

The adaptation of Sponge City principles to Accra's unique context offers an innovative approach to addressing the city's specific hydrological and urban challenges. This paper demonstrates how Accra can mitigate the impact of floods and improve the quality of life for its residents. The findings of this study contribute to the growing body of literature on sustainable urban water management and provide practical insights for policymakers and urban planners in developing countries facing similar challenges.

Figure 1. Map Showing Settlements and Physical Features in the Greater Accra Metropolitan Area (GAMA)

Source: Oduro, et al. 2024

Historical Context of Sponge City Development in China

China's Sponge City initiative was launched in 2014 due to increasing urbanization, frequent flooding, and water pollution. Rapid urban development has replaced natural landscapes with impermeable surfaces, reducing the capacity of cities to absorb and manage stormwater (Chan et al., 2018). The 2012 Beijing flood, which caused 79 deaths and significant economic losses, underscored the need for a new

approach to urban water management(Repnikova, 2019). The Chinese government introduced the Sponge City program to promote sustainable urbanization, enhance flood resilience, and improve water quality through nature-based solutions(Qi, Chan, Thorne, O'Donnell, Quagliolo, Comino, Pezzoli, Li, Griffiths, & Sang, 2020; Song, 2022).

Success Stories of China's Sponge City Initiative

China's Sponge City achieved notable success in several pilot cities. Cities such as Wuhan, one of the first pilot cities, integrated green infrastructures like permeable pavements, rain gardens, and wetlands into their urban design(Peng & Reilly, 2021; Siehr et al., 2022). These measures significantly reduced flooding and improved water quality. Among the positives that can be taken away from the

Wuhan's approach is the construction of over 100 km of permeable roads and 40 km of green belts, significantly reducing flood risks(Han et al., 2023; Li et al., 2021).

Figure 2. Wuhan Sponge Park Research + Visitor Center
Source: ArchDaily, 2023

Shenzhen has implemented large-scale rainwater harvesting and reuse systems, reducing its reliance on traditional water sources and enhancing urban resilience(Wang et al., 2021). Shenzhen has implemented a comprehensive Sponge City plan, including constructing rain gardens, green roofs, and underground storage systems. These measures have reduced urban runoff and improved water quality in the city(Lancia et al., 2020).

While some cities such as Wuhan and Shenzhen focused on Grey, Blue, and green infrastructure, Qingdao focused on restoring natural wetlands and constructing retention basins to manage stormwater. The city also implemented smart water management systems which informed the monitoring and optimization of water use(Ma et al., 2020).

Global Examples of Sponge City Principles

Aside from China's implementation of sponge cities to better manage urban water and protect the environment, there are global examples that point to the effectiveness of sponge cities, this includes Low Impact Development (LID) in cities such as Portland, Oregon, and Philadelphia, Pennsylvania(Dhakal & Chevalier, 2015). These cities have implemented green infrastructure such as rain gardens, permeable pavements, and green roofs. These measures have reduced flooding, improved water quality, and enhanced urban aesthetics(Eckart et al., 2017).

Australia's Water-Sensitive Urban Design (WSUD) approach integrates water management into urban planning. Melbourne implemented WSUD principles for the construction of wetlands, rain gardens, and stormwater harvesting systems. These measures enhanced urban resilience to flooding and drought in the city (Radcliffe, 2019).

In Europe, cities like Rotterdam, Netherlands, and Copenhagen, Denmark, adopted Sponge City principles to address urban flooding. Copenhagen's Cloudburst Management Plan includes the construction of green streets, retention basins, and underground storage systems. Rotterdam also implemented water squares, which serve as public spaces during dry periods and floodwater storage during heavy rainfall (Radcliffe, 2019).

This global acceptance of the Sponge City concept raises endorsed solutions for developing countries to learn from. Considering the established flooding concerns in Accra, adopting the Sponge City concept can address the flooding situation in Accra (Radcliffe, 2019).

Figure 3. Sponge Garden, Rotterdam
Source: DeUrbanisten, 2019

Challenges Faced by China's Sponge Cities and Solutions

The Sponge City Concept (SCC) is currently garnering significant attention, with associated technologies increasingly embraced by municipal governments across China. Initial best practices related to Sponge Cities have begun to be disseminated; however, numerous challenges persist that hinder effective implementation and scaling (Zevenbergen et al., 2018). Among the emerging challenges impeding the continued deployment of Sponge Cities are: (1) the uncertainty surrounding future hydrological conditions linked to climate change projections, which complicates urban planning and the design of infrastructure intended to endure its expected lifespan; and (2) competing priorities among stakeholders, coupled with their reluctance to engage in essential trade-offs, which obstructs future investments in the Sponge City Program (SCP) (Qi, Chan, Thorne, O'Donnell, Quagliolo, Comino, Pezzoli, Li, Griffiths, Sang, et al., 2020). Furthermore, the lack of an integrated and comprehensive model to facilitate Sponge City planning, implementation, and life cycle assessment emerges as a significant hurdle. Ultimately, the complexities surrounding Sponge City planning, implementation, and life cycle assessment are among the most critical challenges faced in this field (Nguyen et al., 2020).

(Nguyen et al., 2020) proposes a novel framework for Sponge City development that integrates four principal sub-models: MIKE-URBAN, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), W045-BEST, and Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA). This integrative approach facilitates the simulation of environmental, social, and economic dimensions pertinent to Sponge City infrastructure, thereby addressing the multifaceted challenges that China's Sponge Cities confront. Conversely, (Guan et al., 2021) conducted a comprehensive environmental assessment and economic analysis aimed at identifying sustainable solutions for the persistent issues faced by Sponge Cities. Their study explored a range of permeable pavement materials, including permeable asphalt concrete, permeable cement concrete, permeable bricks, and innovative pavement materials. Designed to conform to the requisites of infiltration, retention, purification, evaporation, and drainage, these pavement materials exhibit porosity. While the findings indicate that permeable pavements are not inherently more environmentally beneficial than traditional alternatives, they offer significant advantages, such as enhanced water purification, reduction of traffic noise, mitigation of Urban Heat Island (UHI) effects, and facilitation of waste material recycling.

The Need for Sponge City Development in Accra

Accra faces severe flooding issues due to several factors. The destruction of natural wetlands, poor drainage systems, and rapid urbanization contribute to the problem. Additionally, unsustainable environmental practices, such as building waterways, cutting down trees for development, and sand mining. (Amoako & Frimpong Boamah, 2015). The Sponge City concept offers a sustainable solution by reintroducing natural water-holding mechanisms and integrating green infrastructure into urban design. By adopting Sponge City principles, Accra can mitigate flooding, enhance water resource management, and promote sustainable urban development.

Accra needs to adopt the Sponge City principles if it is determined to reduce surface runoff and enhance water infiltration, mitigating the impact of heavy rainfall and reducing flood risks (Attipoe, 2015; Ofosu, 2024). This principle will also reduce the demand for fresh water and promote sustainable water use. Green infrastructure such as rain gardens, green roofs, and wetlands enhance urban biodiversity and improve air quality thereby improving health (Suppakittpaisarn et al., 2017). The principle also encourages the creation of recreational areas that enhance urban aesthetics and provide opportunities for community engagement.

Materials and Methods

The study focused on Accra, Ghana, a city with a population of about four million people, making it the thirteenth (13th) largest metropolitan area in Africa (Gaisie et al., 2019). Characterized by rapid urbanization, poor drainage systems, and frequent flooding.

The metropolis is situated at latitude 00°06'W and longitude 05°35'N. To the north, it borders the Ga West Municipality. On the west, it adjoins the Ga South Municipality, while to the south, it meets the Gulf of Guinea. (Dekongmen et al., 2021)

Data collection was conducted over nine months, from January to October 2024, and included primary and secondary data sources. Primary data were collected through interviews, focus group discussions, and consultations with key stakeholders, including the Ghana Hydrometeorological Agency (GMet), Hydrological Services Department, Local Government Authorities, National Disaster Management Organization (NADMO), and community opinion leaders. Secondary materials were obtained from government reports, existing hydrological studies on Accra and reputable academic databases, including but not limited to Elsevier, Springer Nature, ResearchGate, and Google Scholar. Both primary and secondary data were analyzed concurrently to provide a comprehensive theoretical and empirical assessment of the feasibility of adopting the Sponge City concept from China.

Stakeholder Consultations

Stakeholder consultations were necessary to gather insights on the current state of urban water management in Accra, the challenges of flooding, and the feasibility of implementing Sponge City principles. Stakeholders consulted included: the Ghana Hydrometeorological Agency (GMet), who Provided historical rainfall data, flood risk assessments, and projections on climate change impacts on Accra's rainfall patterns; Local Government Authorities Offered insights into urban planning challenges, drainage infrastructure, and ongoing flood mitigation efforts: the National Disaster Management Organization (NADMO) Shared data on flood incidents, response strategies, and the socio-economic impact of flooding in Accra: Community Opinion Leaders Provided perspectives on community-level challenges, public awareness, and the social acceptability of Sponge City interventions.

Hydrological Measurements

The Ghana Meteorological Agency provided Hydrological data, including rainfall patterns, surface runoff, and groundwater levels, collected using rain gauges, flow meters, and piezometers. while surface runoff and groundwater levels were measured at 11 selected sites across Accra. Measurements were taken weekly to capture variations during the rainy season.

Stakeholder Interviews

Interviews were conducted with 19 key stakeholders, including urban planners, environmental scientists from the Environmental Protection Agency, National Disaster Management Organization, local government officials, and community leaders. The interviews focused on understanding the challenges of urban water management in Accra, the feasibility of implementing Sponge City principles, and potential bottlenecks to adoption.

Figure 4. Flooding in Kaneshi-Accra

Source: Bonaa, 2015

Results

Following discussions with Local Government officials, some historical data on the relationship between population growth and Wetlands, which is also tied to development, came up. They expressed concern about the complete disappearance of numerous wetlands due to rapid urbanization and a lack of regard for their importance. Figure 5 shows the rate of loss of wetlands in the Accra Metropolitan area between 1960 and 2010.

Figure 5. Population Growth Trend of GAMA, 1960-2021
 Source: Oduro, et al. 2024

Efforts to solicit insight into the goal of the paper informed the line of request for vital information needed for this research. There were five key sections for the information request from stakeholders consulted, including Flooding experiences; awareness of the sponge city concept; perception of the sponge city concept; community involvement; and recommendations.

Almost all the stakeholders up to 90% admitted to terrible flood experiences within Accra. 60% admitted that flood occurs more than twice in a year in Accra. The main reasons attributed to these flood experiences are poor drainage systems 70%, destroyed wetlands 50%, heavy rainfall 40%, and noncompliance with building codes among others 30%. This revelation aligns with the literature on the challenges facing Accra concerning consistent flooding.

About 70% of the stakeholders engaged were aware of the sponge city concept. Largely the professionals, engineers, the political class, and experts demonstrate fair knowledge of the sponge city concept. However, some opinion leaders and members of the community had no or little knowledge of sponge city concepts. This indicates the need for public sensitization to ensure public buy-in and participation in sponge city projects.

The primary challenge identified from the stakeholder engagement is the lack of funding. This was attributed to several reasons, the most prominent of which was the country's economic crisis. However, the issue of priority also came up very strongly. Experts emphasized the lack of political will to undertake innovative projects that can solve societal issues such as the flooding that has plagued Accra for some time now.

About 90% of stakeholders showed high levels of interest and willingness to participate in Sponge City projects which is a positive indicator. However, there is a need to clearly define the roles and responsibilities of community members, such as active involvement in planning and maintenance.

Discussion

The prevalence of flooding in Accra screams the urgent need to implement effective flood mitigation strategies. The disappeared wetlands which used to serve as a natural sponge for rainwater absorption have worsened the flood situation in Accra. The problem is further compounded by the poor drainage and rapid urbanization of the city, leading to the frequent flooding experienced. The findings align with

the various literature on Accra flooding issues and highlight the importance of employing natural water-holding mechanisms and improving the drainage infrastructure of the city.

While a majority of stakeholders engaged were aware of the Sponge City concept, a significant portion (30%) had no prior knowledge. This indicates a gap in public knowledge and education about sustainable urban water management solutions. To ensure the success of Sponge City projects in Accra, it is necessary to launch targeted sensitization campaigns that reach a broader audience, including residents, community leaders, and local government officials. Media platforms, community meetings, and educational programs can play a key role in disseminating information about the benefits and principles of Sponge City development. Public understanding and knowledge of nature-based solutions such as the sponge city concept is critical to the step toward solving the flood situation in Accra.

The positive perception of Sponge City solutions among stakeholders is encouraging and suggests strong community support for such initiatives. The potential benefits of reduced flooding and improved water quality, align with the goals of achieving global sustainable urban development. However, the challenges identified, particularly the lack of funding and the absence of good and timely urban planning, must be addressed to ensure the successful implementation of eco-friendly projects. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) and international funding could help bridge the financial gap while revising urban planning policies to incorporate Sponge City principles is critical for long-term success.

Conclusion

Introducing Sponge City principles in Accra offers a sustainable and resilient approach to addressing the city's recurrent flooding problems. This principle addresses the core problems identified by stakeholders and works of literature. By integrating green infrastructure, promoting rainwater infiltration and storage which is absent in the city's current water management infrastructure, and enhancing urban water management, Accra can mitigate the impact of floods and improve the quality of life. Learning from China's experiences and global best practices, Accra can develop a localized Sponge City model to suit Accra's peculiar case and address its hydrological and urban development challenges. Sponge City development has proven to represent a viable and innovative solution to urban flooding problems and Accra's flooding crisis is not an exception. It could pave the way for sustainable development in Accra. Furthermore, this approach aligns with multiple United Nations SDGs, demonstrating its relevance to global efforts to achieve sustainable urbanization, climate resilience, and environmental protection.

There is a need for specific research on policy formulation to include the sponge city concept in policies meant for urban sustainable development. Water management in Accra needs research to properly assess all the possible bottlenecks for the successful implementation of policies that support the sponge city concept.

Acknowledgment

I am grateful to associate professor Li Tian for her invaluable guidance and support throughout this work. My heartfelt thanks also go to the resilient communities and organizations I've collaborated with, whose efforts continue to inspire me. To my two friends and co-authors for their insightful recommendations and participation from the brainstorming to the proofreading. To my family, friends, and peers, thank you for your encouragement and belief in my vision. This publication is a testament to the collective dedication to a sustainable and resilient future.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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